

CUTANEOUS HEMANGIOSARCOMA IN A SHEEP

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Hemangiosarcoma is a malignant tumour of endothelial cells, occurs most frequently in dog and cat (Jin-Kyu Park *et al* 2002) and less commonly in the cow, horse, pig and goat (Raofi *et al*; 2003). A case of cutaneous hemangiosarcoma, in a sheep and its surgical management is reported.

Case history and Observations

A two years old sheep was presented with the history of bleeding from the right fetlock area. Clinical examination revealed a red lump at the fetlock region. It was soft, foul smelling and bleeding was observed when pressure applied. It was decided to perform surgical removal of the growth.

Treatment and Discussion

The animal was prepared for the aseptic surgery as per the routine procedure and surgery was performed under pre-medication using Triflupromazine hydrochloride and local infiltration with 2% lignocaine. Growth was removed by blunt dissection. Cutaneous sutures were applied to approximate the skin edges. Post operatively the animal was treated with Enrofloxacin @ 2 ml / day and Melonex @ 2ml / day intramuscularly for 5 days along with the dressing of the wound with povidone

on alternative days. The animal recovered uneventfully. Sutures were removed on 10th post operative day. The growth for histopathology was fixed in 10% formalin and processed according to routine procedures, and stained with Hematoxylin and Eosine (HE).

Grossly the cut section was characterized by dark reddish parts and multi focal whitish components. Micro-scopically, the vascular spaces lined by elongated endothelial cells with high cellular stroma filled with RBC, necrotic tissue and inflammatory cells were observed. Undifferentiated round, ovoid, and spindle shaped neoplastic cells with pleomorphic, hyperchromatic, large nucleus and scant cytoplasm were also observed. Therefore, based on the histopathological findings the tumour was diagnosed as cutaneous hemangiosarcoma (Moulton, 2001). Cutaneous haemangiosarcomas has the tendency to reoccur after surgical excision and wider spread of local invasion and metastasis (Grant Maxie, 2007). In the present case, the animal was followed for 5 months and no recurrence was observed. The animal recovered uneventfully following surgery with out any post operative complications.

Summary

Successful surgical management of

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cutaneous hemangiosarcoma in a sheep is described and discussed.

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